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Electronic and I.R. Spectra of Some Transition Metal Complexes of Triazene-1-Oxides

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WHILE reviewing the studies done on the coordination complexes of triazene-1 oxides (TH) [I,II] we noted that the electronic and i.r. spectra of some transition metal complexes are not yet available in the literature. We report the relevant spectra of oxovanadium(IV), iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) chelates and some mixed chelates with dipyriddy/ *o*-phenanthroline.

Results and Discussion

A. Electronic Spectra : (i) Oxo-vanadium (IV) Complexes [VOT₂] :

Nujol mull spectra of several substituted triazene-1-oxide complexes show two well resolved bands around 16 kK and 25 kK. According to the model proposed by Ballhausen and Gray¹ these two bands are assigned to : $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ transitions. Apparently the first transition $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$ is not observed. Superimposable electronic spectra (Table I) and i.r. spectra are obtained for oxovanadium(IV) complex of

TABLE I—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) COMPLEXES OF TRIAZENE-1-OXIDE

Complex	R	Ar	Electronic Spectral bands in kK	Transitions
VOT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	16.0 26.6	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$
VOT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (p)	16.1 26.0	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$
VOT ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	16.1 26.6	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$
VOT ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (p)	16.1 26.6	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$

a given triazene-1-oxide irrespective of whether the complex is obtained from vanadyl sulphate or from ammonium vanadate. The first electronic transition gives the value of 10 Dq which is comparable to that (16 kK) observed for [VO(H₂O)₅]²⁺. This indicates that the ligand field strength of the bidentate triazene-1-oxides is comparable to that of H₂O—a conclusion arrived at by Behera and Chakravorty² from a comparison of the electronic spectra of [Cr(H₂O)₆]³⁺ (10 Dq=17.4 kK) and [CrT₃] (R=alkyl, Ar=aryl) (10 Dq=17.4 kK).

(ii) Mixed Chelates of Cobalt(II) [CoT₂.dipy/ *o*-phen] :

The electronic spectra of two mixed chelates of cobalt(II) containing two 1,3-diphenyl triazene-1-oxides and one dipy/ *o*-phen were run in nujol mull as well as in acetone solution. Unfortunately only one high energy absorption band around 25 kK and one broad and weak band centered around 10.5 kK could be detected. Besides, some slight structures are observed around 16.5-18.0 kK. The low energy transition around 10 kK may be assigned to ν_1 (${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$) while the second may be ν_2 (${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$). Introduction of strong field

dipy/*o*-phen evidently raises the ν_1 transition compared to that of $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ at 8.1 kK.

(iii) *Iron(III) Complexes* :

Behera⁸ had reported magnetic moments (around 5.92 B.M.) and electronic spectra of three iron(III) complexes. The electronic transitions observed in benzene solutions have extremely high extinction coefficients (3200-43000), which were assigned to metal $\leftrightarrow$ ligand redox transitions. Since the literature does not record any study of iron(II) complexes of these ligands, we reacted ferrous ammonium sulphate with 1,3-diphenyl triazene-1-oxide. The complex so obtained has satisfactory analyses for a formula $[\text{FeT}_3]$. The solid state spectrum of $[\text{FeT}_3]$ obtained from (a) ferrous ammonium sulphate was exactly similar to that obtained from (b) ferric ammonium sulphate. The band positions at 18.1 kK are the same as reported by Behera³ in benzene solution. The magnetic moments of the two preparations (a) and (b) are 5.98 and 6.09 B.M. respectively. The m.p.s of the two preparations compare well with that reported by Behera (153°). We are thus convinced that ferrous iron reacts with triazene-1-oxide in air to produce ferric derivative of triazene-1-oxides.

B. *Infrared Spectra* :

The very first infrared spectrum of a triazene-1-oxide complex, namely that of oxovanadium(IV) $[\text{VOT}_2]$, was published by Dutta and Lahiry⁴. As these authors were pre-occupied with the idea of establishing the identical nature of the complex obtained from (a) vanadyl sulphate and (b) ammonium vanadate, they did no more than to present the two superimposable infrared spectra of (a) and (b). The only band they identified was that of VO at 980 cm^{-1} . In these two spectra there appeared a sharp band at around 2934 cm^{-1} which could be mistaken as $\nu(\text{NH})$ band. Irrespective of these ligands having hydroxy triazene structure or triazene-1-oxide structure, this range should look transparent after complexation. Through oversight the authors failed to mention whether the spectra were run as KBr disc or as nujol mull. We had re-run these spectra in both KBr and nujol. In KBr no such band appears but it does so in nujol. Thus the (2934 cm^{-1}) band in the reported spectra is due to the CH stretch of nujol itself. Since no serious assignment of the different bands has so far been made either for the triazene-1-oxide ligands or their complexes, we endeavour to do so in the present communication. The

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT I.R. BANDS OF OXOVANADIUM(IV), IRON(III), COBALT(II) (HOMO AND MIXED CHELATES), NICKEL(II) AND COPPER(II) COMPLEXES OF TRIAZENE-1-OXIDES.

Compound	$\nu\text{N-H}$	$\nu\text{C-C}$ (phenyl)	$\nu\text{-N=N-N-}$ (sym. triazene)		$\nu\text{N}\rightarrow\text{O}$	$\nu\text{C-C}$ (in plane)	$\nu\text{dipy}/\text{o-phen}$	
1,3-diphenyl triazene-1-oxide (TH)	3160s	1600s	1510s,	1475b,	1440s	1300w	1220b	—
VOT_2	—	1600s	1482s,	1463w,	1380s	1240s	—	—
FeT_3	—	1590s	1482s,	1462w,	1375s	1235s	—	—
CoT_3	—	1590s	1480s,	1460w,	1385s	1235s	—	—
CoT_3 , dipy	—	1590s	1480s,	1460w,	1370s	1240s	—	1430s, 1170b, 730s
CoT_3 , <i>o</i> -phen	—	1590s	1480s,	1460w,	1370s	1240s	—	1425s, 1170b, 730s
NiT_3	—	1590s	1480s,	1460s,	1370s	1235s	—	—
CuT_3	—	1595s	1485s,	1465s,	1370s	1240s	—	—
3- <i>p</i> -tolyl-1-phenyl triazene-1-oxide (TH)	3180s	1605s	1527s,	1475b,	1430s	1305s	1215b	—
VOT_2	—	1595s	1510s,	1490w,	1465w	1245s	—	—
FeT_3	—	1595s	1510s,	1490w,	1465w	1245s	—	—
CoT_3	—	1595s	1512s,	1490w,	1462w	1245s	—	—
CoT_3 , dipy	—	1595s	1510s,	1490w,	1465w	1250s	—	1430s, 1170b, 730s
CoT_3 , <i>o</i> -phen	—	1595s	1510s,	1490w,	1465w	1245s	—	1430s, 1170b, 730s
NiT_3	—	1595s	1510s,	1490w,	1465w	1245s	—	—
CuT_3	—	1595s	1510s,	1490w,	1465w	1245s	—	—

s = strong ; b = broad ; w = weak.

expected i.r. bands for ν_{N-H} (3200 cm^{-1}) ν_{C-C} (phenyl ring) (1600 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{-N=N-N-}$ (sym. triazene; ($\sim 1560 - 1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$ ($\sim 1300 - 1220\text{ cm}^{-1}$) have all been located in the i.r. spectra of the triazene-1-oxide ligands⁵. $\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$ band is found to be considerably lowered ($\sim 60\text{ cm}^{-1}$) due to N-O-M bond formation⁶⁻⁸. ν_{N-H} band of the ligand completely disappears in the complexes MT_2 , MT_3 and MT_4 (dipy/*o*-phen) showing coordination of the metal ion through N-atom. ν_{C-C} (phenyl ring) remains almost unchanged ($\sim 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$). $\nu_{-N=N-N-}$ is lowered by $\sim 26\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to change in the environment of the symmetric triazene. The $\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$ (1300 cm^{-1}) is lowered to ($\sim 1240\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Both in the homochelates and the mixed chelates the very sharp new band around ($\sim 1240\text{ cm}^{-1}$) also covers a few weak bands as well as ν_{C-C} (phenyl in plane). Characteristic bands of coordinated dipy/*o*-phen as in $[Cu(dipy)Cl_2]$ and $[Cu(o\text{-phen})Cl_2]$ ⁹; $[Ni(OH_2)Cl(dipy)_2]Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$ ¹⁰ around $\sim 730\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\sim 1170\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1470\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed in the spectra of $[CoT_2(dipy/o\text{-phen})]$ complexes. The important i.r. bands have been presented in Table 2.

Experimental

The chelates were prepared by following standard procedures^{4,11,12}. Their characterisation data were satisfactory. Room temperature magnetic moments were measured in Gouy balance using $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as a calibrant. The electronic spectra were run at SIC, Madras and i.r. spectra at C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of bis(ethylmalonato) Co(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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BETA-diketones and beta-keto esters have drawn considerable attention as oxygen donorchelating ligands¹⁻⁶. We have been trying^{7,8} to prepare complexes with nitrogen donors of these metal chelates. We thought it would be worthwhile to extend our investigation to the synthesis of a number of mixed ligand complexes of Co(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions with malonic ester and nitrogen donor aliphatic and heterocyclic amines.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The metal chelates were prepared as reported earlier⁷. Mixed ligand complexes were prepared by refluxing an ethanolic suspension of metal chelates and amines in 1:2 ratio for about two hours over water bath. On keeping the resulting solution overnight, crystalline compounds separated out which were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution. Electronic spectra were recorded in M/100 chloroform solution of the complexes. All the relevant analytical and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

Result and Discussion

All the twelve complexes reported in the present communication have the composition $[ML_2B_2]^0$, where M=Co(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II); L is malonic ester and B is either a heterocyclic or aliphatic amine. Cobalt complexes are brown, copper complexes are green and zinc complexes are white in colour and these complexes have fairly low melting points. Acetone solution of the complexes are found to be non-electrolytes as the ΔM values range between 8 to 12 mhos cm^2 . The μ_{eff} values for Co(II) and Cu(II) complexes are around 5.1 and 1.8 B. M. respectively. In I. R. spectra of the mixed ligand complexes the two bands $\nu(C=O)$ at 1600 cm^{-1} and $\nu(C-O)$ at 1290 cm^{-1} are again shifted to higher frequency regions appearing around 1620 and 1310 cm^{-1} respectively indicating bonding of the σ -bonded amines to the metal ions. Moreover, most of the bands due to nitrogen bases, have been modified in the complexes which indirectly supports the bonding of the nitrogen donor ligands to metal ions. Further, the direct evidence of bonding of oxygen and nitrogen